

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

FAIR Assessment – ESRF-PaNOSC Pilot - Conceptual Requirements

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0.1	Init	2025/12/16	Add benchmark references. Fill core generic (Gen2) and specialized metrics.	Renaud Duyme
1.0	Ready	2026/06/29	Finalize pass/fail examples, test impl references.	Renaud Duyme

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ESRF	Renaud Duyme	0000-0002-9909-1074	Writing – review & editing

Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
GUPRI	Globally unique, persistent and resolvable
GUID	Globally unique and resolvable. Note that often people use this (mistakenly) interchangeably with GUPRI.

PaNET	Photon and Neutron Experimental Techniques
ESRF	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility

FAIR Assessment – ESRF-PaNOSC Pilot - Conceptual Requirements.....	1
Introduction and Task Management	2
Overview	4
Summary of component types.....	4
Understanding and using this template	5
Types of Metrics	6
Symbols	6
Generic Metrics.....	6
Specialised Metrics	6
Refinements and sufficiency	6
Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset	7
Related Records.....	7
Description.....	7
Applicability.....	7
Benchmark screenshots	8
Guidance.....	8
FAIR Principles F1: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers ..	8
FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers	8
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence - Gen2-MI-F1B	9
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	9
Guidance	9
Test Reference.....	9
FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers	9
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A.....	9
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	10
Guidance	10
Test Reference.....	10
FAIR-F2: data are described with rich metadata	10
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata	11
Related Records	11
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	11

Guidance	11
Test Reference.....	12
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata	12
Related Records	12
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	12
Guidance	12
Test Reference.....	13
FAIR-F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	13
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata.....	13
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	13
Guidance	13
Test Reference.....	13
FAIR-F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	14
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata indexed in a searchable resource	14
Differences from the Generic Metric	14
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	14
Guidance	14
Test Reference.....	15
FAIR-A1: (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	15
FAIR-A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.....	16
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval.....	16
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	16
Guidance	16
Test Reference.....	17
FAIR-A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	17
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization	17
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	17
Guidance	17
Test Reference.....	18
FAIR-A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	18
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence.....	18
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	18
Guidance	18

Test Reference.....	19
FAIR-I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	19
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft).....	20
Differences from the Generic Metric	20
Related Records	20
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	20
Guidance	20
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict).....	21
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	21
Guidance	21
Test Reference.....	21
FAIR-I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	21
Specialised Metric: DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET	22
Description.....	22
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples.....	22
Guidance.....	23
Test Reference FAIR champion.....	23
FAIR-I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	23
FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links.....	23
Related Records	23
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	23
Guidance	24
FAIR-R1: (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	24
FAIR-R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	25
Differences from the Generic Metric	25
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	25
Guidance	26
FAIR-R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	26
Specialised Metric Name: The dataset is cited in a publication	26
Related Metrics.....	26
Description.....	26
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	26
Guidance	27
Specialised Metric Name: Author affiliation is defined in metadata	27

Related Metrics.....	27
Description.....	27
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	27
Guidance	28
Test Reference FAIR Champion:.....	28
Specialised Metric Name: Funding information is defined in metadata	28
Related Metrics.....	28
Description.....	28
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	29
Guidance	29
FAIR-R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.....	29

Introduction and Task Management

This document describes a FAIR benchmark and its associated components, tailored to the needs of the ESRF (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility). ESRF is a member of the Photon and Neutron Open Science Cluster (PaNOSC). This document is a human-readable, narrative description of this community's requirements for FAIR assessment of datasets, without the inclusion of technical details. It follows the [Assess-IF](#) and, once complete, can be used as a starting point for the creation of required technical components.

The following arguments should be passed to this benchmark:

- **Mandatory:** The GUPRI (or other identifier such as URL) for the digital object being assessed.
- **Optional:** The FAIRsharing URL or DOI for the database that stores the digital object being assessed. While not required, passing this argument will allow more information about the digital object and its holding database to be retrieved.

This document was created using a template found at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17901311>. This template can be copied and used within any community to begin preparations for a FAIR benchmark specific to your needs.

The tables below should be used to keep track of your progress and provide attribution.

FAIR Assessment Conceptual Components - Roadmap		
Task	Status	Notes
1: Benchmark – narrative requirements	Completed	Mark as complete when Benchmark section in this document is completed. Iterative refinement may be required before completing step 4.

2: All metrics - narrative requirements	Completed	Mark as complete when all metric sections in this document are completed. Iterative refinement may be required before completing step 4.
3: Related standards, databases and collections - registration with FAIRsharing	Completed	<p><i>Any standards, databases and collections that are required for the correct running of your benchmark should be registered with FAIRsharing and listed in the 'Related Records' area of the metrics sections.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/6443 - ESRF - Resources for FAIR Assessment
4: Completed first draft of document	Completed	Once all parties are happy with this document, the first draft is complete, and the next task may begin.
5: Benchmark - registration with FAIRsharing	Completed	<p><i>Provide the URL for your FAIRsharing Benchmark record here, or a link to e.g. a spreadsheet containing this information.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/6477 - Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset
6: All metrics - registration with FAIRsharing	Completed	<p><i>Provide the URLs for your FAIRsharing metric records here, or a link to e.g. a spreadsheet containing this information.</i></p> <p>Generic Metrics:</p> <p>Gen2-MI-F1B FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence</p> <p>Gen2-MI-F1A FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness</p> <p>Gen2-MI-F2A FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata</p> <p>Gen2-MI-F2B FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata</p> <p>Gen2-MI-F3 FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata</p> <p>Gen2-MI-A1-1 FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval</p> <p>Gen2-MI-A1-2 FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization</p> <p>Gen2-MI-A2 FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence</p> <p>Gen2-MI-I1B-Strict FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict)</p> <p>Gen2-MI-I3 FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links</p> <p>Specialized Metrics:</p> <p>FM F4 M DOI OA ESRF The content associated to a DOI is Open Access</p> <p>FM I2 M VOC-PANET DOI ESRF DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET</p> <p>FM R1-2 M Fund ESRF Funding information is defined in metadata</p> <p>FM R1-1 M DOI Lic ESRF License is defined in the DOI metadata</p>

		FM R1-2 M Affil ESRF Author affiliation is defined in metadata
		FM R1-2 D CITED-BY-PUB ESRF : The dataset is cited in a publication

Overview

The Assessment Interoperability Framework (Assess-IF) being used by this community aims to create a uniform approach for defining and running tests (and specifically FAIR tests in the context of this document) by:

1. **Giving the community the power to choose what FAIR means to them:** Until now, using a FAIR tool such as those listed at <https://fairassist.org/tools> meant either selecting from among the benchmarks for FAIR that a given tool provides (which may be unclear or hard to understand exactly what's being tested) or a formal collaboration with tool(s) to ensure they provide a custom FAIR assessment solution for your needs. The Assess-IF allows you to explicitly state how your community defines FAIR, and exactly how it should be tested, measured, weighted and scored.
2. **Encouraging transparency in assessment behaviours:** To date, FAIR assessment has been characterised by disparate behaviours and scores arising from independently authored FAIR Assessment tools, which themselves vary in the level of transparency they exhibit for their tests and benchmarks. The Assess-IF methodology encourages all tools and assessment platforms to register their assessment components (e.g. benchmarks, metrics) in a searchable manner, with rich metadata explaining what is being tested, why, and how. The Assess-IF allows you not only to define FAIR according to your community requirements but also provides a way of making those definitions clear, visible, reusable and extendable. Benchmarks that cannot be discovered via a search, and do not describe themselves sufficiently, do not themselves meet the minimum expectations for FAIRness and make it harder to understand if a particular tool interprets FAIR the way your community requires it to be interpreted.
3. **Defining a consistent report format for assessments:** Because the reports are designed to be understood by any tool, the user can have a wider range of independent tools to select from. Being able to move these reports from one tool to another also allows the user to contextualise their tests, and to explore results from different perspectives.
4. **Enabling Automatic FAIR Testing via APIs:** by creating shared APIs among the different domains (FAIR, SKG, DMP, maDMP) it becomes possible to “embed” assessments into existing tooling. For example, a DMP authoring tool will be able to “call out” to a FAIR Assessment tool to obtain real-time information about the FAIRness of a digital object while the DMP is being written or updated.

Summary of component types

The Assess-IF has seven main “components”, split according to three main categories: **conceptual** components define FAIR for a community in human-readable terms, **software** components provide the actual tests and interpretations of those tests, and **data** components store the results of running an assessment. This template helps you to fully specify the conceptual components for your community definition of FAIR and gives you jumping off points to create the software components and ultimately run assessments to produce data in the form of test results. As such, we have provided a short description of each component so that you can understand the wider framework at a very high level.

The **conceptual components** are:

1. **Dimensions/principles:** Dimensions (for this template, our dimensions are the FAIR Principles) are designed to be subject- and implementation-agnostic criteria or high-level goals that may be refined for particular communities as described in this template. More information on the FAIR principles can be found in the FAIR Principles FAIRsharing record (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.WWI10U>), which provides a wealth of information about them as well as linking to individual records describing all sub-principles.
2. **Benchmarks:** Community-specific groupings of metrics. They provide a narrative describing how a community defines FAIR. Communities can choose the granularity of their benchmarks with regards to subject area and digital object type. Specifically, this means that benchmarks may be agnostic of object type or subject area, or may be scoped as tightly as required by the benchmark authors.
3. **Metrics:** Narrative description that a Test must wholly implement. Each metric should implement exactly one dimension (e.g. one sub-principle from the FAIR Principles). Metrics may be domain-agnostic or not.

A detailed understanding of the remaining components (below) is not required for the purposes of this template, but a short description of each is provided for completeness.

The **software components** are:

1. **Tests:** The instantiation of metrics, executed to assess a digital object in accordance with the metric linked to the test.
2. **Scoring Algorithms:** The instantiation of benchmarks, executed to create community-specific value judgements on the outcomes of tests. They specify the exact set of tests which are to be run by the assessment service together with weightings for each of these tests. Algorithms contextualise the sum of all test results for a given benchmark into a final quantitative assessment result.

The **data components** are:

1. **Test Results:** The output of running a test over a digital object. A test result also contains provenance metadata about the process followed to create it.
2. **Test Result Sets:** A set of test results, together with their respective metadata.
3. **Benchmark Scores:** Obtained after executing a scoring algorithm over a set of test results. The benchmark score includes a value, a log and a link to the test results used to obtain the score.

Understanding and using this template

After making a copy of this file for your own use, please complete the sections according to how FAIR should be defined for your digital research object of interest.

This template is organised into multiple sections to help you define your conceptual components and begin to think about your software components. It is deliberately written without exposing too much of the underlying framework, to simplify the task of creating your specific FAIR requirements. When complete, you will not only have defined your Assess-IF conceptual components, but you will also be ready to begin the iterative development of the software components.

There is one benchmark section followed by metric sections named according to the FAIR principle they implement. If you have more than one metric for any principle, please add sub-headings within its section.

Types of Metrics

Symbols

- indicate a Generic metric.
- indicates a Specialised metric.
- indicates a section providing more information.

When a community uses this document to describe a benchmark and related metrics, the metrics can be one of two types.

Within OSTRails, all principles have corresponding **generic metrics** except for the following: I2, R1.2, R1.3, which communities must **specialise** for their requirements. Such specialised metrics generally need to consider the requirements of both the specific discipline and digital object type being assessed by the benchmark.

Generic Metrics

If a section is labelled **generic**, then all benchmarks should be able to implement the generic metric rather than needing to define a community-specific metric. Generic metrics are those that cover domain-agnostic features, therefore applicable to any discipline, irrespective of the type of digital object being evaluated.

Specialised Metrics

 If a section is labelled **specialised**, then the principle is considered highly domain specific, and we suggest that all communities create their own metric to suit their requirements.

Refinements and sufficiency

Small modifications to existing generic metrics may optionally be added as **refinements** to a generic metric within a community document. These are intended to allow communities to specify exactly where a field can be found, e.g. a licence field, within their metadata. These will either be implemented as a specialised test (rather than using the already-created generic test associated with

a generic metric) or as a specialised metric. Iterative updates to this document will determine which is appropriate.

While the classification of **generic** and **specialised** metrics is useful and is intended to make it easier to create assessments, there will be circumstances where a given **generic** metric is a *necessary* part of the assessment for a community but is also *insufficient* to wholly describe that community's requirements for that principle.

For example, perhaps a community wishes to specifically check for a particular type of DOI (e.g. one minted by an approved service of their choice) in addition to the presence of any GUPRI type ("any GUPRI" is the definition of the generic F1 GUID metric). In such a case, **refinements** are not appropriate (because the underlying generic metric is *necessary* but not *sufficient*); instead, **specialised** metrics linked to a principle that already has a **generic** metric are appropriate. In this example, the community should use two metrics, both of which are linked to FAIR F1-GUID: one will be the **generic** metric for FAIR F1-GUID and the other will be a new **specialised** metric with the added requirement.

Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset

Related Records

FAIRsharing records relating to the benchmark:

- *Benchmark – FAIR ESRF Dataset*: <https://fairsharing.org/6477>
 - The benchmark mainly defines a list of metrics.
 - Generic metrics (Gen 2). All of them are covered by default by DataCite DOIs
 - Specialized metrics.
- *Scoring algorithm*: [ESRF Benchmark Scoring Algorithm](#)
 - The scoring algorithm defines how test associated to the benchmark metrics will execute and score in a FAIR assessment tool. We use [FAIR Champion](#) tool.
- *ESRF - Resources for FAIR Assessment* (FAIRsharing collection): <https://fairsharing.org/6443>
 - A simple collection of assets.

Description

The *Benchmark – FAIR ESRF Dataset* assesses ESRF dataset metadata quality. It is of primary utility for ESRF Data Catalogue (<https://data.esrf.fr/>) managers and users (scientists). This benchmark coordinates the FAIR assessment of ESRF dataset metadata. Metrics selected support FAIR assessment based on DataCite DOI metadata.

Applicability

What *digital object(s)* will be covered?

Datasets.

What *subject area(s)* are covered by this benchmark?

Photon and Neutron community datasets

Benchmark screenshots

Benchmark – FAIR ESRF Dataset: <https://fairsharing.org/6477>

General information	Metrics list
<p>RELATED CONTENT</p> <p>Search through related fairassist components</p> <p>ARDS (0) RELATED DATABASES (1) RELATED FAIRASSIST COMPONENTS (15)</p> <p>FAIR Metric - DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset has associated metric FAIR Metric - DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET</p> <p>FAIR Metric - The content associated to a DOI is Open Access Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset has associated metric FAIR Metric - The content associated to a DOI is Open Access</p> <p>FAIR Metric - The dataset is cited in a publication Benchmark - FAIR ESRF Dataset has associated metric FAIR Metric - The dataset is cited in a</p>	

Guidance

The FAIRsharing benchmark will be used to document the benchmark

FAIR Principles F1: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a2cea7>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic** and is implemented via its sub-principles (see the next two sections).

This principle is very commonly split into its distinct components of the identifiers being 1) GUPRIs, and 2) persistent. As such, the **generic metrics** in use for F1 are also split between sub-principles F1-GUID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>) and F1-PID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>).

FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence - Gen2-MI-F1B

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

 For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VRo9Dl>.

 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered: a DOI is a PID
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_identifier_persistence

FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A

- This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.
- For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK>.
- For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered: DOI is GUID
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_unique_identifier

FAIR-F2: data are described with rich metadata

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic** and is implemented in two parts, via two metrics (see the next two sections).

The two **generic** metrics separately deal with the identified metadata being 1) structured (F2A, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2dUpZs>), and 2) grounded (F2B, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.lXAOU2>).

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2dUpZs>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- ~~This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.~~
- ~~This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.~~

Related Records

FAIRsharing records relating to the specialised metric:

- e.g., the particular vocabularies required by your community, if **applicable**

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered: Content Negotiation as application/ld+json linked data
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_structured_metadata

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IXAOu2>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- ~~This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.~~
- ~~This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.~~

Related Records

FAIRsharing records relating to the specialised metric:

- e.g., the particular vocabularies required by your community, if **applicable**

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered: Content Negotiation as application/ld+json linked data
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_grounded_metadata

FAIR-F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5Xy1dJ>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.820324>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered: DOI reference is contained in metadata
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_identifier_in_metadata

- Note: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/FAIR-Core-Tests/issues/16>

FAIR-F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata indexed in a searchable resource

- This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.
- For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.x1f1l4>.
- For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- ~~This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.~~
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- ~~This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.~~

Differences from the Generic Metric

This section should be removed from your document if you are using the generic metric without modification, or if this principle and associated metric are not applicable to your community.

Description of differences:

- We want to check the dataset metadata is indexed.
- We also want to check that the dataset content is open access. See metric: <https://fairsharing.org/6449>

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	ESRF Dataset are open access
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- *FAIR Champion:* https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_open_access_publication

FAIR-A1: (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7014eb>.

The metrics relating to this principle are **generic** and are implemented via sub-principles (see the next two sections).

This principle is into two distinct components, which require that the protocol being used to retrieve the (meta)data 1) is openly specified, thus making them open, free and universally implementable, and 2) clearly states the procedures for access, including authentication/authorisation where required. As such, the **generic metrics** in use for A1 are also split between sub-principles A1.1 (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>) and A1.2 (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>).

FAIR-A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.DfMGZW>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- ~~This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.~~
- ~~This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.~~

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-1634389699	DataCite DOI covered.
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- **FAIR Champion:** https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_protocol

FAIR-A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VrP6sm>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/esrf-es-2210534378	DataCite DOI covered.
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- **FAIR Champion:** https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_data_authorization

FAIR-A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- ~~This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.~~
- ~~This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.~~

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/esrf-es-2120018741	DataCite DOI covered.
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_persistence

FAIR-I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648>.

The metrics relating to this principle are **generic**.

There is a choice of two **generic** metrics that implement this principle. Each community should choose either the *soft* (with a looser interpretation of FAIR I1) or *strict* (with a more precise definition of FAIR I1) version of the metric depending on their needs. As such, the **generic** metrics in use for I1 are either the *soft* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.qUroF6>) or the *strict* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.l8fVBn>). You should pick one, and will not need both.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft)

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Differences from the Generic Metric

This section should be removed from your document if you are using the generic metric without modification, or if this principle and associated metric are not applicable to your community.

Description of differences:

- We use , *FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict)*, below

Related Records

FAIRsharing records relating to the specialised metric:

- e.g., the particular vocabularies required by your community, if applicable

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict)

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/esrf-es-2120018741	DataCite DOI covered: Content Negotiation as application/ld+json linked data
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/assess/test/fc_data_kr_language_strong

FAIR-I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

💡 This metric is **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metric in a way appropriate to their needs. While **generic** metrics exist, we strongly suggest **specialised** metrics are always created, even if a **generic** metric is also chosen.

📦 For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af>.

For completeness, we note that **generic** metrics are available for this principle: a loose and a strict metric. However, we strongly recommend that you also specialise this metric to provide additional restrictions on the specific vocabularies that your community requires. Therefore, we have included both **generic** and **specialised** sections within this principle heading.

Please first provide a **specialised** metric for I2. Optionally, you may also choose between two **generic** metrics that implement this principle: the *loose* (with a looser interpretation of FAIR I2) or *strict* (with a more precise definition of FAIR I2) metric, depending on your needs. As such, the **generic** metrics in use for I2 are either the *loose* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.E3Nr1d>) or the *strict* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.RCUvvt>). You should pick one; you will not need both.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statements.

- Our community will not use any **generic** metric for I2 and will only use the **specialised** metric described below.
- ~~Our community will use the *loose* **generic** metric in addition to the **specialised** metric described below.~~
- ~~Our community will use the *strict* **generic** metric in addition to the **specialised** metric described below.~~

Specialised Metric: DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET

Description

DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET (<https://fairsharing.org/6465>).

Important to track datasets related to our community and encourage dataset reused.

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/esrf-es-2120018741	https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.15151/ESRF-ES-2120018741 . See test impl. request
Negative	10.5281/zenodo.15388270	https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15388270 . See test impl. request
Indeterminate	10.1039/D5NR02241J	Indeterminate Crossref DOI not in DataCite

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference FAIR champion

- Test impl. request: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/Community-FAIR-Tests/issues/12>
- <https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/>
 - DCAT: https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_panet_vocabulary_in_metadata

FAIR-I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.LLXjWx>.

For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ae22b8>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

- This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.
- This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.
- This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.

Related Records

FAIRsharing records relating to the specialised metric:

- e.g., the particular vocabularies required by your community, if applicable

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.

Status	URI	Description
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Positive	10.15151/esrf-es-2120018741	DataCite DOI covered: Content Negotiation as application/ld+json linked data
Negative	n/a	
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference

- [FAIR Champion: https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_outward_links](https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_outward_links)

FAIR-R1: (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

Metric R1.1 is **generic**.

💡 Metrics R1.2 and R1.3 are **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metrics for R1.2 and 1.3 in ways appropriate to their needs.

📖 For more information on the top-level principle R1, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.821487>.

Please note that you may wish to implement a metric that addresses R1 as a whole or, alternatively, create metrics that individually address R1.2 and R1.3. You should not need to do both.

FAIR-R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

This is a **generic metric**. If it does not match your community requirements, then specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

📖 For more information on this **generic metric**, including documentation and justifications, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.YAdSwh>.

📖 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.aff99f>.

Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement.

This generic metric **is sufficient** for our needs.

This generic metric **is not sufficient** for our needs and we will describe the differences in the next section.

Differences from the Generic Metric

This section should be removed from your document if you are using the generic metric without modification, or if this principle and associated metric are not applicable to your community.

Description of differences:

- We want to check the license the DOI metadata. See metric : <https://fairsharing.org/7465> : License is defined in the DOI metadata

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/esrf-dc-2170175685	License in DataCite Metadata. See: test implementation request
Negative	10.15468/sjkrht	No license in DataCite Metadata. See: test implementation request

Indeterminate	10.19276/plinius.2025.01.014	Non Crossref or DataCite DOI. See: test implementation request
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Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference FAIR Champion:

- test implementation request: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/Community-FAIR-Tests/issues/4>
- <https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/>
 - DCAT: https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_license_information

FAIR-R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

💡 This metric is **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metric in a way appropriate to their needs.

📦 For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3e9860>.

Specialised Metric Name: The dataset is cited in a publication

Related Metrics

- <https://fairsharing.org/7466> : The dataset is cited in a publication. Useful for dataset reused

Description

This metric evaluates whether the research object provided by the supplied DOI has been formally recognised and cited within the scholarly literature.

Why does your community care about this principle?

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric.

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-DC-572252655	The dataset is cited, (OpenAlex source). See: test implementation request
Negative	10.15151/ESRF-ES-2120018741	The dataset is not cited
Indeterminate	n/a	

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference FAIR Champion:

- test impl. request: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/Community-FAIR-Tests/issues/1>
- <https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/>
 - DCAT: https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_data_cited_in_pub

Specialised Metric Name: Author affiliation is defined in metadata

Related Metrics

- <https://fairsharing.org/7494> : Author affiliation is defined in metadata

Description

The Metric expects a URL or DOI and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to. It checks the author affiliation is defined in metadata.

Why does your community care about this principle?

Better track science output authorship

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric.

Examples

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15468/sjkrht	Affiliation in DataCite metadata. See: test implementation request
Positive	10.1063/5.0095229	Affiliation in Crossref metadata. See: test implementation request
Positive	10.1038/nature24679	Affiliation in DOI landing page meta tag : citation_author_institution. See: test implementation request
Negative	10.1016/S0969-2126(02)00850-X	No affiliation in Crossref metadata. See: test implementation request
Indeterminate	10.19276/plinius.2025.01.014	Medra DOI, (not Crossref DOI, not DataCite DOI). See: test implementation request

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference FAIR Champion:

- Test impl. request: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/Community-FAIR-Tests/issues/7>
- <https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/>
 - DCAT: https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_metadata_includes_author_affiliation

Specialised Metric Name: Funding information is defined in metadata

Related Metrics

- <https://fairsharing.org/7496/> : Funding information is defined in metadata

Description

This metric ensures that the research object provided by the supplied URL or DOI has metadata containing funding information.

Why does your community care about this principle?

Better track science output funding

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples

Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects that pass or fail the metric.

Examples

Status	URI	Description
Positive	10.15151/ESRF-ES-2303075148	Funding reference in DataCite metadata. See: test implementation request
Negative	10.15151/ESRF-DC-572252655	No funding reference in DataCite metadata. See: test implementation request
Indeterminate	10.19276/plinius.2025.01.014	Medra DOI, (not Crossref DOI, not DataCite DOI). See: test implementation request

Guidance

Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):

- A DOI exists for all datasets in ESRF Data catalogue.

Test Reference FAIR Champion:

- test impl. request: <https://github.com/wilkinsonlab/Community-FAIR-Tests/issues/8>
- <https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/>
 - DCAT: https://tests.ostrails.eu/community-tests/community_metadata_includes_author_affiliation

FAIR-R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

💡 This metric is **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metric in a way appropriate to their needs.

📖 For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.87d197>.

A specialised metric is not applicable for now for ESRF: <https://fairsharing.org/6465> best suits for I2 than for R1.3